

HEALTH HAZARDS EXPERIENCED BY SELECTED 10TH STANDARD STUDENTS WHILE CARRYING SCHOOL BACKPACKJayshree Rodge¹, Jyoti Munde² and Swati Suryavanshi³

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Abstract

The present investigation entitled "Health Hazards experienced by selected 10th standard students while carrying school backpack" was undertaken by conducting survey among sixty high school going boys and girls between 13- 16 yrs. age who were using backpacks. Thirty boys and 30 girls each studying in high school 10th standards from different schools of Parbhani town were selected for this study. The findings revealed that mean average scores for health hazards and frequencies of experience for 10th standard boys while carrying school backpacks indicated higher values of frequencies for stress on the spine, tiredness, stiffneck, and headache. Mean average scores for health hazards and frequencies of experience for 10th standard girls while carrying school backpacks indicated higher values of frequencies for chest pain, headache, tiredness, red marks on the shoulder, stress on spine, stiffness of neck, and numbness. Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between frequency scores and health hazards of boys and girls for numbness, stomach pain, chest pain, and headache while carrying school backpacks. It was observed that age of the 10th standard boys was positively correlated with health hazard red marks on the back and negatively correlated with stiff neck, and headache, while BMI of the boys was negatively correlated with numbness. The age of girls had a negative correlation with headache. Weight and BMI of 10th standard girls showed a negatively significant correlation with injuries on fingers.

Key Words: Health hazards and Backpack**Introduction**

Human beings are engaged in different types of activities throughout their life. Daily they perform manual activities such as carrying and moving loads by pushing, pulling, lifting and putting down. Activities performed by manually life handling of load are a part and parcel of our life. Right from morning till getting the bed ready to sleep at night body of human being is busy in great number of manual activities.

Students of all ages hold a schoolbag containing textbooks, notebooks, library books, geometrical and numerical instruments, and other materials. The backpack is one of the several forms of manual load carriage that provides versatility and often used by hikers' backpackers, soldiers, as well as by school Children (Knapik et al 1996).

According to Ramprasad and Raghuveer (2009), a child's spine is particularly vulnerable to problems because their muscles are still developing and their bones will not fully harden until their mid-twenties. By flattening the lumbar region and rising the curve in the thoracic region, this may change the natural curvature of the spine. Since a child's spine still has a lot of cartilage, it's very susceptible to repeated micro-trauma and resulting weakening. High loads and poor back posture cause the spine and its tissues to stiffen and distort, potentially leading to possible injuries (Kim et al 2008). This can result in not only pain and discomfort, but also a lack of balance (Cavallo 2002).

Proper backpack use should be emphasized in the school years as pain during youth is also associated with pain as a young adults, other reason that justifies the study is that students of 10th standard suffer mostly because there is sudden increase in their backpack weight as they promote to the next class. There are very limited research studies available on the effect of backpacks on health of school going students.

Objective: To study the health hazards of selected 10th standard students while carrying school backpack.

Methodology**Selection of the Sample**

The present investigation was conducted in the Parbhani town of Marathwada region in Maharashtra state. Thirty Boys and 30 girls studying in 10th standard, aged between 13 – 16 yrs. were selected from different schools of Parbhani town.

Equipments used for collecting data:

1) Weighing machine 2) Anthrop meter 3) Measuring tape

Method of data Collection

The study was comprised of survey to find out detailed information of the high school going students and asking them a series of questions regarding health hazards of selected 10th standard boys and girls.

Body mass index

Body mass index (BMI) was calculated by using the following Formula

Weight (Kg)

$$\text{BMI (kg/m}^2\text{)} = \frac{\text{Weight (Kg)}}{\text{Height (m)}^2}$$

Height (m)²

Health hazards experienced by high school going students

Frequency of health hazards experienced by selected high school boys and girls was collected on three point scale as always, some times and never with respective score of 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Correlation Co-efficient

Correlation co-efficient was calculated for describing the degree of correlation between dependent and independent variables in the study were age, weight, and BMI of selected high school going student. Correlation co-efficient was calculated by using the following formula

$$r(x,y) = \frac{\text{Covariance (X,Y)}}{\sqrt{\text{Variance (x), Variance(y)}}}$$

Results

It was noticed that majority of the selected boys (60%) and girls (70%) of the 10th standard were in the obese grade I category having body mass index between 25.0 – 30.0 kg/m², followed by boys (30%) and girls (10%) in the obese grade II category having body mass index more than 30.0 kg/m². Boys (10%) girls (20%) were in the normal category having body mass index between 20.5 – 25.0 kg/m². Health hazards and frequency of experience by selected high school going students of 10th standard while carrying a school backpack Findings related to health hazards and frequency of experience by selected high school going students of 10th standard while carrying a school backpack are given in table 1. It is clear from the table that cent percent of the boys were always had stress on spine, followed by an equal percents (80%) experienced red marks on back and stiffness in neck, also an equal percentages (70%) had experienced red marks on shoulders, headache and tiredness, while 60 per cent of them experienced chest pain. Fifty per cent of them experienced injuries on fingers. An equal percentage (40%) had experienced numbness, tired

eyes and stomach pain.

As regards 10th standard girls, cent percent of them experienced stress on spine, stiff neck, chest pain and headache, followed by 80 per cent experienced numbness and red marks on shoulders. An equal percentage (70%) experienced red marks on back and tiredness, 40 per cent experienced injuries on fingers and tired eyes, whereas only 30 per cent experienced stomach pain.

Mean average scores for health hazards and frequencies of experience for 10th standard boys while carrying school backpacks indicated higher values of frequencies for stress on the spine (2.6), tiredness (2.2), stiff neck (2.1), and headache (2.1). Mean average scores were lower for chest pain (1.9) red marks on the shoulders (1.8) red marks on the back (1.8), stomach pain (1.8), injuries on fingers (1.5), numbness (1.4) and tired eyes (1.4) while carrying school backpacks. Mean average scores for health hazards and frequencies of experience for 10th standard girls while carrying school backpacks indicated higher values of frequencies for chest pain (2.8), headache (2.7), tiredness (2.6), red marks on the shoulders (2.5), stress on spine (2.3), stiffness of neck (2.3), and numbness (2.0). Mean average scores were lower for red marks on the back (1.7), tired eyes (1.5), injuries on fingers (1.4), and stomach pain (1.3) while carrying school backpacks.

Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between frequency scores and health hazards of boys and girls for numbness (2.479*), stomach pain (2.475*), chest pain (4.663**), and headache (3.260**) while carrying school backpacks.

Correlation of age, weight, and BMI with the frequency of health hazards experienced by selected high school going students of 10th standard while carrying a school backpack

Data about correlation of age, weight, and BMI with the frequency of health hazards experienced by selected high school going students of 10th standard while carrying a school backpack is presented in table 1. It is clearly seen from the table that age of the 10th standard boys was positively correlated with red marks on the back (1.00**) and negatively correlated with stiff neck and headache (-0.608* and -0.612* respectively), while BMI of the boys was negatively correlated with numbness (-0.613*). Age of the girls had a negative correlation with headache (-0.654*) and weight and BMI of

10th standard girls showed a negatively significant correlation with injuries on fingers (-0.605* and -0.603* respectively).

Conclusions

It is concluded that mean average scores for health hazards and frequencies of experience for 10th standard boys while carrying school backpacks indicated higher values of frequencies for stress on the spine, tiredness, stiff neck, and headache. Mean average scores for health hazards and frequencies of experience for 10th standard girls while carrying school backpacks indicated higher values of frequencies for chest pain, headache, tiredness, red marks on the shoulder, stress on spine, stiffness of neck, and numbness. Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between frequency scores and health hazards of boys and girls for numbness, stomach pain, chest pain, and headache while carrying school backpacks.

It was observed that age of the 10th standard boys was positively correlated with health hazard red marks on the back and negatively correlated with stiff neck, and headache, while BMI of the boys was negatively correlated with numbness. The age of girls had a negative correlation with headache. Weight and BMI of 10th standard girls showed a negatively significant correlation with injuries on fingers.

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Table 2 : Correlation of age, weight, and BMI with the frequency of health hazards experienced by selected high school going students of 10th standard while carrying a school backpack

Health Hazards	Boys (N=10)			Girls (N=10)		
	Age	Weight	BMI	Age	Weight	BMI
Numbness	-0.166 ^{NS}	-0.548 ^{NS}	-0.613*	0.200 ^{NS}	-0.136 ^{NS}	-0.216 ^{NS}
Red marks on shoulder	0.408 ^{NS}	-0.434 ^{NS}	-0.446 ^{NS}	-0.218 ^{NS}	0.282 ^{NS}	0.264 ^{NS}
Red marks on back	1.000**	0.513 ^{NS}	0.544 ^{NS}	0.218 ^{NS}	-0.505 ^{NS}	-0.482 ^{NS}
Injuries on Fingers	0.492 ^{NS}	0.289 ^{NS}	0.216 ^{NS}	0.185 ^{NS}	-0.605*	-0.603*
Stress on Spine	0.430 ^{NS}	0.067 ^{NS}	0.022 ^{NS}	-0.200 ^{NS}	-0.209 ^{NS}	-0.269 ^{NS}
Tired eyes	0.304 ^{NS}	-0.245 ^{NS}	-0.173 ^{NS}	0.258 ^{NS}	0.224 ^{NS}	0.192 ^{NS}
Stiff Neck	-0.608*	0.029 ^{NS}	0.057 ^{NS}	-0.218 ^{NS}	-0.340 ^{NS}	-0.280 ^{NS}
Stomach Pain	0.304 ^{NS}	0.382 ^{NS}	0.437 ^{NS}	-0.333 ^{NS}	-0.069 ^{NS}	-0.118 ^{NS}
Chest Pain	0.068 ^{NS}	0.531 ^{NS}	0.544 ^{NS}	0.218 ^{NS}	0.336 ^{NS}	0.351 ^{NS}
Headache	-0.612*	-0.418 ^{NS}	-0.438 ^{NS}	-0.654*	-0.127 ^{NS}	-0.167 ^{NS}
Feeling of tiredness	0.430 ^{NS}	0.345 ^{NS}	0.290 ^{NS}	-0.218 ^{NS}	-0.236 ^{NS}	-0.249 ^{NS}

NS- Non Significant, *- significant at 5% level, **- Significant at 1% level

Table 1 : Health hazards and frequency of experience by selected high school going students of 10th standard while carrying aschool backpack

Sr. no	Health hazards	Frequency of Health hazards										't' value
		Boys (N=10)					Girls (N=10)					
		Total N=10	Mean	Always	Sometimes	Never	Total N=10	Mean	Always	Sometimes	Never	
1	Numbness	4 (40)	1.4	---	4(40)	6(60)	8(80)	2.0	1(10)	7(70)	3(30)	2.479*
2	Red marks on shoulder	7 (70)	1.8	1(10)	6(60)	3(30)	8(80)	2.5	7(70)	1(10)	2(20)	2.095 ^{NS}
3	Red marks on back	8 (80)	1.8	---	8(80)	2(20)	7(70)	1.7	---	7(70)	3(30)	0.465 ^{NS}
4	Injuries on fingers	5 (50)	1.5	---	5(50)	5(50)	4(40)	1.4	---	4(40)	6(60)	0.434 ^{NS}
5	Stress on spine	10 (100)	2.6	6(60)	4(40)	---	10(100)	2.3	3(30)	7(70)	---	1.345 ^{NS}
6	Tired eyes	4 (40)	1.4	---	4(40)	6(60)	4(40)	1.5	1(10)	3(30)	6(60)	0.336 ^{NS}
7	Stiff Neck	8 (80)	2.1	2(20)	6(60)	2(20)	10(100)	2.3	3(30)	7(70)	---	0.769 ^{NS}
8	Stomach Pain	4 (40)	1.8	2(20)	2(20)	8(80)	3(30)	1.3	---	3(30)	7(70)	2.475*
9	Chest Pain	6 (60)	1.9	3(30)	3(30)	4(40)	10(100)	2.8	8(80)	2(20)	---	4.663**
10	Headache	7 (70)	2.1	4(70)	3(30)	3(30)	10(100)	2.7	7(70)	3(30)	---	3.260**
11	Tiredness	7 (70)	2.2	5(70)	2(20)	3(10)	7(70)	2.6	6(60)	4(40)	---	2.051 ^{NS}

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages, NS- Non Significant, *- significant at 5% level, **- Significant at 1% level